

A Study on Role of Women Empowerment in Indian Armed Forces

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Abstract

Women empowerment is essential for upliftment of economic, social status of women. In the modern world, there are no occupations that women have not delved into. Mainly, the Indian armed forces, which was a male dominated work place now has confident, bold women, molding into every aspect. This current study will evaluate the role of Indian women in the armed forces and highlights the challenges faced by the women in Armed Forces. This study reveals the constitutional provisions for the empowerment of women in Indian armed forces. This study concludes that Women are contributing significantly to the militaries all over the worlds including India.

"When women are wearing the uniform, there is no difference between men and women. Women discharge their duties as male officers do".

Introduction

Women empowerment refers to the spiritual, political, social educational, gender of individuals and communities of women. In India, women empowerment depends upon geographical location, educational status, social status and age. Women empowerment is essential for upliftment of economic and social status of women.

In the modern world, there are no occupations that women have not delved into. Mainly, the Indian armed forces, which was a male dominated work place now has confident, bold women, molding into every aspect. The entry of women in armed forces, for a long time, was limited only to the medical profession i.e. doctors and nurses. The doors were open in the year 1992 for women in the armed forces.

Review of Literature

Cook (2006) enunciates that women hit many roles in the military for over 3,000 years in a large number of cultures and nations. Although various limited roles in the armies of past societies, the role of women in the military, peculiar in combat was very constraint, and it is only now recently that woman have been given attention and prominent role in armed forces.

In the Report (Categories of Entry, 2011) it has been reported that Indian Armed Forces categorized into three professional uniformed services: the Indian Army, the Indian Navy, and the Indian Air Force. The extent of Indian Armed Forces is over 1.3million active

personnel. It is the world's 3rd largest military force and has the world's largest volunteer army. Indian Army comprises of 1, 12, 88,900 active personnel and 9, 90,960 as reserve. Indian Navy has a strength of 58, 350 active and 55,000 as reserve personnel. Indian Air Force has strength of 1, 27,200 as active and 1, 40,000 as reserve.

The article (Deccan Herald, 2012) disclosed that women officers in the Indian Army, Navy and Air Force make up only 3.3, 3.9 and 10.4 percent of the officer cadre respectively. The appearance of women in the armed forces for a long time, was constrained to the medical profession i.e., Doctors and nurses. In 1992, the doors were thrown open for women entry as general officers in aviation, logistics, Law engineering and executive cadres. Thousands of enthusiastic young women applied against advertisements and it was a turning point in the antiquity of time. These women prefer a new field where they had to painstakingly pave a path for the others to pursue.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the role of women in Indian Armed Forces.
2. To analyze the obstacle in the path of women empowerment in Indian Armed Forces.
3. To assess the employment of women in combat will be the major aspect of the study.

Research Methodology

This paper is descriptive in nature. This paper tries to analyze the empowerment of women Indian Armed Forces. The sources of this study are the books, periodicals and newspapers according to need of this study.

The Role of Women in Indian Armed Forces

Presently, women in non-medical cadre, serve as Short Service Commissioned (SSC) officers. Under this type of commission, they can assist in the armed forces for a period ranging from 5-14 years. On release they can pursue a career in the civil sector.

Qualified women can join in the following branches of Indian Armed Forces

Army: Engineers, Army education corps, Army Ordnance Corps, Army Service Corps and Intelligence

Navy: All branches of Navy (Except submariners and divers)

Air Force: Flying, Technical and Administrative

Coast Guard: All branches of Coast Guard

To mention, a list of women who initiated history in Indian Armed forces

- Priya Jhingan made history when she became the first cadet to join the Indian Army in 1992.
- Punitha Arora, the first female Vice Admiral to Indian Navy
- Padmavathy Bandopadhyaya is the first woman Air Marshal of the Indian Air Force.
- Divya Ajith Kumar created a history by becoming the first women in the Indian Army to receive the coveted 'Sword of Honour'
- Shanthy Tigga became the first Jawaaan of Indian Army.
- Nivedita Choudary the first woman officer in the Indian Air Force to summit Mt. Everest.

Women in Armed Forces

The strength of women officers and male officers in the Armed Forces is given below:

S.No.	Category	Women	Men
1	Indian Army: (Excluding Medical, Dental and Nursing)	1561	41074
2	Indian Air Force (Excluding Medical, Dental branch)	1594	10781
3	Indian Navy (including Medical and Dental officers)	644	10652

Source: Press Information Bureau, Government of India, Ministry of Defence, 12th March 2018.

Why women should consider joining the Indian Armed Forces?

1. The branch of Army is highly regarded work place for women to serve as military nurse.
2. President Pranab Mukherjee declared that women will be allowed in combat roles. Women can fly fighter planes in the Indian Air Force.
3. There is no inequality in pay. All the officers of equal rank get the same salary.
4. Everyone gets equivalent opportunity to flourish.
5. Women employees are involved in teaching Army Education Core.
6. All officers, men and women leading a big troop is the best way to absorb team spirit and leadership (administrative) values.
7. The Armed Forces allows women to study at the same time while serving the Army
8. Famous Women contingents are making headlines all around.

Constitutional Provisions for empowerment of women in Armed Forces

In 1992, pinnacle in the history of Indian Army was the entrance of women into the officer cadre initiated by the Indian Army.

- Constitution of India gives freedom to practice any profession, put to carry on any occupation, trade and business.
- The constitution mandate that the Indian Air Force to induction of lady officers in 1992 in different branches.
- Short Service Commission (SSC), in the Regular Army will be granted for 14 years.
- Span of training 49 weeks
- Substantive Promotion to SSCOs.

Challenges faced by women in Indian Armed Forces

Women have been serving in militaries world over for over a century. They have come through in supportive roles in military health, logistics, education and aviation. The following are the issues and challenges faced by women in Indian Armed Forces:

- (i) **Physical Issues**
The natural physical differences in stature, strength and body composition between the sexes make women more sensitive to certain types of injuries and medical problems.
- (ii) **Physiological Issues**
The natural process of menstruation and pregnancy make women weak in combat situations.
- (iii) **Social and Psychological Issues**
Women tend to be more attached to their families, especially children. This turns into greater mental stress and need of social support to sustain themselves at the time of prolonged separations from family.
- (iv) **Nutritional Issues**
Nutritional supplementation of women combatants, especially iron and calcium, and in some countries Vitamin D may help prevent injuries and ill health. Ensuring a healthy and balanced diet is important for maintaining positive health.

- (v) Designing battle equipment that improves performance of women combatants
Lighter and more comfortable combat gear and footwear to fit the female form could significantly enhance the performance and make the difference between life and death in combat situations. Female-specific field hygiene equipment is also something that is being seriously considered and can prevent a number of medical problems.

Findings

- Now a day's women are participating in the armed forces effectively.
- The findings also reveal that women are physically and mentally fit to perform the combat role in the armed forces.
- The number of women recruited in armed forces has increased significantly over the past few decades.

Conclusion

Women are contributing significantly to the militaries all over the worlds including India. The present study revolves around the possibilities of combat role for women in Indian Armed forces. The views of the people are overwhelming towards the combat roles for the women in Armed forces. The Changing environment, security perception and the capabilities of the women has made them eligible to work in the armed forces in combat roles.

“When women are wearing the uniform, there is no difference between men and women. Women discharge their duties as male officers do”.

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